

HORIZON 2020
The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation

Project acronym: VALUECARE
Grant Agreement Number: 875215
Project full title: Value-based methodology for integrated care supported by ICT
Call identifier: H2020-SC1-DTH-11-2019

D7.5 Report on the contribution to standardisation

Version number: 1.1
Status: Final
Dissemination Level: Public
Due date of deliverable: 30.11.2021
Actual submission date: 30.11.2021
Project Officer: Elisa Irlandese
Work Package: WP7
Lead partner for this deliverable: KVC
Partner(s) contributing: ECHA, FBK, VIDAVO, EMC, MEDRI, AULSS2, CDC, ISRAA, AMC

Main author(s):

Mireia Ferri	KVC	Maite Ferrando	KVC
--------------	-----	----------------	-----

Contributing author(s):

Demi Cheng	EMC	Elena Procaccini	AULSS2
Nikos Kavoulis	AMC	Lovorka Bilajac	MEDRI
Stefania Macchione	ISRAA	Miriam Fernández	UVEG
Esmee Bally	EMC	Andrew Darley	UCD
Sofia Ortet	CDC	Karolina Mackiewicz	ECHA

Reviewers:

Elena Procaccini	AULSS2	Oscar Mayora	FBK
------------------	--------	--------------	-----

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

History

Date	Version number	Change
August 21	0	Structure of the deliverable and templates for collecting information from pilot sites
Sept –Oct 21	0.1	Content development with inputs from pilot sites
2 November	0.2	Version for internal reviewers
08 November	0.3	Inputs received from Demi Cheng (EMC)
11 November	0.4	Inputs received from the reviewers (ULSS + FBK)
12 November	0.5	Included inputs missing from UCD
19 November	0.6	Included missing inputs from MEDRI and CDC
23 November	0.7	Include the reviewers' recommendation "Ensure that D7.5 describes also a realistic roadmap of actions focusing on delivering towards standardisation"
25 November	0.8	Version to final check by the quality team
29 November	0.9	Minor edits
30 November	1	Final version to be submitted
30 November	1.1	Inputs received from the PC

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The D7.5 “Report on the contribution on standardisation” presents the first attempt to existing standards related to ValueCare approach and its potential contribution to ongoing and further standards after two years of project implementation. Concretely, the **main objective** of D7.5 is to facilitate the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the ValueCare developed solutions; and consequently, **two specific objectives** were identified: (i) To provide starting information for other WPs, ensure compatibility and interoperability with what already exists in the market through standards; and (ii) To use the standardisation system as a tool for dissemination of the project results and interaction with the market stakeholders. For that, two mutually linked **activities** had been implemented: Subtask 7.5.1. Identification and analysis of related existing standards, and Subtask 7.5.2. Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from the results of the project, including the collaboration with the relevant standardisation Technical Committees. The **methodology** to implement both activities required the participation of ValueCare consortium, specially: (i) pilot sites who identified relevant standardisation bodies at their national context and the instruments they are using to evaluate the impact of the ValueCare in their target groups (older person, informal caregivers, and health and social professionals), (ii) EMC as leader of the WP on evaluation, and (iii) technological partners; all these together with a deep analysis of already submitted deliverables in terms of contribution to standardisation.

The **main outcomes** of the analysis performed are the following:

- ▶ A further exploration should be done with the definitive versions of some of the already analysed deliverables, also considering the common standards at technological level to allow ValueCare solution integration with other systems.
- ▶ ValueCare can contribute to the validation of some existing standards and questionnaires used to measure the clinical information at pilot sites in the framework of the ValueCare evaluation (WP5). A contribution to existing common standards on health data should be explored.
- ▶ ValueCare data management policy has been developed to be compliant with FAIR principles with relevant implications in standardisation.
- ▶ Standardisation bodies at European and national level (considering the countries of the ValueCare consortium) were mapped as an initial step to further engage them in concrete activities to be performed during the coming months.

As **recommendations**, authors highlight the following:

- ▶ In the ValueCare questionnaire some small adaptations were made to the ICHOM data set for older persons; this should be evaluated and reported as part of the validation among ValueCare pilot sites.
- ▶ Athens and Coimbra pilot sites plan to include questionnaire items to measure the acceptancy/usability of the technological solution among the target groups. This approach can be considered among other pilot sites of the ValueCare study as well, and EMC as leader of the WP5 on evaluation can propose and discuss this.

The **intended audience** of this report is: the ValueCare consortium, in particular, EMC as responsible of the evaluation, pilot sites, and ECHA as leader of the WP7 on exploitation. Moreover, the deliverable is also intended to external agents as standardisation bodies who can collaborate with ValueCare or stakeholders interested in standardisation related to health and social care, researchers in the field, and technological providers and developers that can link their solutions with the ValueCare digital solution and vice versa.

Some **further steps** are being identified in this report in a roadmap towards standardisation to be implemented in the coming months to provide the final version of this deliverable at the end of the project (Month 54).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction to the ValueCare project	6
1.1	Objectives of the project	6
2	Introduction to the deliverable	7
2.1	Deliverable objectives and scope	7
2.2	Relation to other WPs and deliverables	7
3	Methodology.....	9
4	Identification and analysis of related existing standards (Subtask 7.5.1).	11
4.1	WPs needs in terms of standardisation	11
4.2	Existing common standards.....	15
4.2.1	Existing common standards in health and social care.....	15
4.2.2	Existing common data standards on health.....	17
4.2.3	Existing common standards at technological level applied to ValueCare digital solution 18	
4.3	Standardisation committees and related organisations	19
4.3.1	Standardisation bodies at EU level	19
4.3.2	Standardisation bodies at National level	20
4.4	Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from the results of the project (Subtask 7.5.2).....	27
5	Roadmap towards standardisation.....	30
6	Findings and conclusions	32
7	References	34

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1:	Relation to other WPs	8
Table 2:	Validated instruments and standards used at ValueCare pilot sites to measure the needed data identified in WP2	14
Table 3:	Validated instruments to measure variables identified in the WP5.....	14
Table 4:	ICHOM data set for older person domains and relation with the ValueCare questionnaire for older person	17
Table 5:	ELOT certifications applied to health and social care	20
Table 6:	technical commissions working in the health and social care	21
Table 7:	IPO certifications applied to health and social care	21
Table 8:	Certifications applied to health and social care	22
Table 9:	existing standardisation applied to health and social care.....	24
Table 10:	NEN certifications applied to health and social care	25
Table 11:	AULSS2 certifications.....	26

Table 12: AENOR certifications applied to health and social care 27

Table 13: Translated versions of validated instruments to be used during the ValueCare implementation phase. 29

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AMQP - Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
D – Deliverable
FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation
HL7 - Health Level Seven

ICHOM – International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measures
JSON – JavaScript Object Notation
NoSQL – Not only SQL (Structured query language)
TRL – Technology Readiness Level
WP – Work Package

1 Introduction to the ValueCare project

Healthy ageing along with independent living have become fundamental challenges for Europe as all EU member states (and virtually every country in the world) are experiencing growth in the number and proportion of older persons in their population. Several international organisations (Council of Europe, 2014; International Longevity Centre Brazil, 2014; WHO, 2002) have remarked the importance of the independence, participation and autonomy of older people to remain healthy and, consequently, to ensure their quality of life.

The WHO (2002) defines health as "...a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease". The idea of health as the absence of disease has long been considered insufficiently broad and not covering all aspects of health. Unfortunately, it is at present likely unobtainable for many, particularly with the rise in chronic disease and an aging population, with many people with multi-morbidity and frailty who require a coordinated care plan involving numerous health providers, social and other care services. The concept of health promoted by WHO is also hard to measure, is not tailored to the individual and, according to some authors, of limited use for assessing whether a health system is providing value to citizens. Greater acknowledgment of areas of wellbeing providing wider value to older people and those with chronic illnesses, such as societal participation and coping capacity, may allow for a more practical and thorough assessment of value in healthcare, particularly in high-income countries. Shilton et al. (2011) propose a definition of health focussed on giving people the income, education, and power to control their lives, highlighting the role of supportive systems, environments, and policies in enabling health.

In this context, ValueCare's vision of healthy ageing is that any older individual in society can live the best life possible according to what they value, facilitated by access to high quality, person-centred, evidence-based and affordable health and social care services, supported by strong and integrated health and social services. ValueCare partners believe that taking an "enhanced value-based approach" (including not only health but also lifestyle and social care in the concept of value-based care) supported by secure and robust digital technologies will help to achieve this. In addition, the project will also consider the job satisfaction and the wellbeing of the health and social service providers. Not only satisfying the Triple Aim, i.e. (i) improving the experience of care (including quality and satisfaction); (ii) improving the health of populations; and (iii) containing and potentially reducing, by means of a better use of the available resources, the per capita cost of care, which mainly focuses on the person's side, but taking also into account the care providers and integrating their satisfaction in the job and wellbeing in order to truly optimize ValueCare's performance.

1.1 Objectives of the project

ValueCare addresses Horizon 2020 Call: SC1-DTH-2018-2020 – Digital transformation in Health and Care. The project aims to deliver personalised integrated (health and social) care services, better outcomes for citizens, improved care experience, improved staff satisfaction and greater efficiency in the use of resources and coordination of care in a setting that ensures trust of users and policy makers with regard to data access, protection and sharing and which can be replicated and deployed at large scale in other EU countries. In alignment with the above, ValueCare will focus on the following general objectives:

- ▶ Objective 1. To deliver efficient outcome-based integrated (health and social) care to older people suffering from cognitive impairment, frailty, and multiple chronic health conditions in order to improve their quality of life (and of their families)
- ▶ Objective 2. To contribute to the sustainability of health and social care systems in Europe
- ▶ Objective 3. To provide a secure, scalable, and robust digital solution for integrated care

2 Introduction to the deliverable

2.1 Deliverable objectives and scope

This deliverable D.7.5 “**Report on the contribution on standardisation**” is part of the task 7.5 **Standardisation activities** under the **WP7 Exploitation, innovation, and business models**. In this sense, D.7.5 supports the **general objective 3** “To provide a secure, scalable and robust digital solution for integrated care” contributing to the **specific objective 3.3** “To provide a scalable digital solution for integrated care while contributing to standards on this field” identifying and analysing ValueCare related existing standards, and the contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation providing an overview of the existing standards related to ValueCare and the potential contribution of the project to these standards and future standardisation.

The **main objective** of the task 7.5 is to facilitate the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the ValueCare developed solutions. In this line, **two specific objectives** were identified:

1. To provide starting information for other WPs, ensure compatibility and interoperability with what already exists in the market through standards.
2. To use the standardisation system as a tool for dissemination of the project results and interaction with the market stakeholders.

To fulfil the above objectives **two specific activities** had been considered inside the task 7.5, being mutually linked:

- ▶ Subtask 7.5.1. Identification and analysis of related existing standards.
- ▶ Subtask 7.5.2. Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from the results of the project, including the collaboration with the relevant standardisation Technical Committees.

In this sense, this report presents the first attempt to existing standards related to ValueCare approach and its potential contribution to ongoing and further standards after two years of project implementation. The final version of this deliverable will be provided at the end of the project (Month 54).

2.2 Relation to other WPs and deliverables

This deliverable is strongly linked with the following WPs and deliverables (Table 1).

WP	Deliverable	Relationship
WP ₂	D.2.2 Identify data needed	In this deliverable the minimal clerical and clinical data needed from ValueCare pilot sites is identified and provides a timeline for the required data. The relation with this deliverable is linked to the potential standards identified in D.2.2.
WP ₃	D3.2 Technical Requirements of Architecture	In this deliverable the technical requirements of the ValueCare digital architecture are presented aimed to support the use of industry standard application interfaces, or Software Development Kits, where available for communication among the software and hardware. This supports the greatest possible interoperability with third party hardware. In this sense, the use of standards should be reported in this deliverable to further analyse their exploitation opportunities among the WP7.
	D.3.3. Conceptual design	This deliverable defined the overall technical architecture of ValueCare system; for further exploitation, it is important to describe how it can be integrated to other systems either connecting to them or augmenting it with

		external functionalities to further exploit the potential exploitation opportunities among the WP7.
WP4	D.4.2 Implementation plan for each pilot site	In this deliverable, pilots described their individual plans to implement the ValueCare solution. Some of them also included extra questionnaires and instruments that will be used in specific pilot sites according to their target population. Those questionnaires/instruments should be reviewed in terms of their contribution to standardisation in this deliverable D7.5.
WP5	D.5.1 Agreed-upon pilot sites evaluation framework	In this deliverable the common evaluation framework to all ValueCare pilot sites is defined with the questionnaires to be used. These questionnaires are analysed in this deliverable to explore how the ValueCare project contribute to their validation in other settings and languages.
WP7	D.7.4 Strategy for VALUECARE replication and exploitation roadmap	Not available at the moment of this deliverable writing.
WP8	D.8.7 and D.8.8. Data management	These deliverables include information about data management during and after the project, methodology and standards to be used. The identified standards in these deliverables should be again analysed here to explore the contribution of ValueCare project to existing standards and the potential building of new ones.

Table 1: Relation to other WPs

3 Methodology

As mentioned, this deliverable presents the work done under the task 7.5 after two years of ValueCare project implementation. This task is subdivided in two mutually linked subtasks that had been implemented following the steps described below:

Subtask 7.5.1. Identification and analysis of related existing standards.

As a first step, an analysis of the (confidential and public) already **submitted deliverables** had been made to detect any standardisation implication and needs. In particular, the following deliverables were reviewed:

- ▶ D2.2. Identify data needed
- ▶ D3.2 Technical Requirements of Architecture
- ▶ D3.3. Conceptual design
- ▶ D4.2 ValueCare Implementation plan for each pilot site
- ▶ D5.1 Agreed-upon pilot sites evaluation framework
- ▶ D8.7 and D8.8. Data management plan

When needed, authors of this deliverable asked for clarifications to the leaders of the above deliverables or pilot sites via email and sharing the deliverable in the common ValueCare repository. Partners have access to preliminary versions of this deliverable and were able to complete the missing data.

In parallel, a **mapping exercise** was performed by KVC, pilot sites and technological partners to identify European and national standardisation bodies and existing standards applicable to ValueCare approach related to health and social field, data sharing and technology. For that, KVC:

- ▶ Shared with pilot sites a dedicated template to identify the national existing certification bodies or similar entities interesting to be mapped for performing networking activities in the next steps of the project.
- ▶ Asked pilot sites to report any existing standards they use in the health and social field but also in terms of data to be reported.
- ▶ Asked technological partners to report on existing standards they are using to develop the ValueCare solution to explore the potential contribution of the project to this domain.

A next step to be performed in further versions of this deliverable is to ask **WP leaders and corresponding partners in charge of those analysed deliverables** to complete the evaluation to provide a deep overview of the WPs needs in terms of standardisation. Also, the section about the existing common standards at technological level should be included in the next version of this deliverable and the activities to be performed once the mapping is done should be defined among partners and implemented to be reported in the next version of this deliverable. The initial analysis of existing standards will be also completed with a deep review of existing standards on health, data, and technology in particular with the close collaboration of technological partners.

Subtask 7.5.2. Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from the results of the project, including the collaboration with the relevant standardisation Technical Committees.

As a result of previous task, partners have mapped **national and international standardisation bodies** that can be engaged in the ValueCare project activities, in particular, in the exploitation actions foreseen in the next months under the WP7. A dedicated mailing list with the contacts reported by pilot sites is being compiled and the activities to involve them are being designed together with ECHAlliance as leader of the WP7.

In this subtask, the following sub-tasks had been also performed:

- ▶ Followed the discussion among pilot sites about the consideration of the ValueCare as **medical device** according to their national legislation.
- ▶ Monitored the need of pilot sites of **translating the questionnaire** proposed by EMC as leader of the WP5 on evaluation, to analyse the potential contribution of ValueCare to the validation of existing indexes not validated at country languages. In addition, **extra indexes** were identified with the same purpose.
- ▶ First overview of the **roadmap towards standardisation** to be followed during the coming months.

As **next steps** to be done under this task, the following had been agreed:

- ▶ Networking activities design and implementation with related standardisation technical committees already identified in this deliverable.
- ▶ Exploring how ValueCare is contributing to identified standards and potential building of new ones.
- ▶ Engaging the Advisory Board as key actor in previous both tasks, in particular the chair of the board because of her relationship with ICHOM.

4 Identification and analysis of related existing standards (Subtask 7.5.1).

As described in the methodology section, an initial analysis of the standardisation landscape has been performed, starting from the needs of other ValueCare WPs about existing standards that can be related, as well as existing standards in the health and social field, and data. The following two subsections presents the results obtained in this initial analysis.

4.1 WPs needs in terms of standardisation

In this section the WPs needs analysis is detailed identifying the deliverables reviewed in each WP:

WP2 – Development of new integrated care built on value-based methodology to be implemented at EU level -> D2.2- Identify data needed

In this deliverable the clerical and clinical data is defined as follows:

Clerical information comprises all on personal data (but excluding data specifically about health or social care, and clinical information), record keeping, appointments, coordination, and systems for guaranteeing the communication within teams and services and with key persons outside the organisation (meetings, calls, etc.), book-keeping and, if applies, invoicing systems.

Clinical information consists of information ranging from determinants of health and measures of health (risks) and wellbeing to documentation of care delivery.

The above kind of information is expected to be collected at pilot sites level guaranteeing the security of all sensitive information while ensuring agile sharing.

D2.2 defines the variables among both kinds of information. Among the clerical information common information on personal, administrative, socio-economic, and socio-demographic data is collected. So, no standards are applicable. However, among the clinical information some validated indexes are used to measure different variables in all pilot sites and additional validated questionnaires are identified in some pilot sites to measure concrete variables (Table 2). In this sense, it is important to mention that the D2.2 will be updated in the D2.9 in May 2022 so the detected variables can be modified; so potential changes will be analysed in the next version of this deliverable (D7.6).

WP3 – Digital IT for Value-based Integrated Care -> D3.2 Technical Requirements of Architecture

The aim of D3.2 is to specify the technical requirements of the essential elements of architecture that needs to be developed for the ValueCare Digital solution based on the integration on existing systems (Vida24™ - TRL 9; and Horus AI – TRL7). Vida24™ can bridge to any **Electronic Health Record / Health Information System (EHR/HIS) system**; is **GDPR** compliant (Registered to Hellenic Data Protection Authority Directory); and has a **European Conformity (CE) Class IIa certification**. Vida24® provides application programming interfaces (**API's**) for integration to existing systems.

In this sense, the development of the digital solution is close linked with the use of common standards to allow the integration of existing systems, data collected at pilot sites, further data from new commers in the exploitation phase of the solution, etc.

The following system components had been described in the D.3.2 that can also contribute to the data standardisation in ValueCare to the extent that the final solution can be interoperable and integrated with other data, open sources, etc.:

► **Database:**

- Use of **MongoDB** by the virtual coach database, a NoSQL database that can store a large amount of data with high availability and scalable performance.

- ▶ Use of **MySQL**, an open-source relational database management system (RDBMS), of Vidaz4 to hold health and wellbeing data from ValueCare.
- ▶ **Messages** by the virtual coach platform to interact with other services:
 - ▶ Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (**AMQP protocol**), an open standard application layer protocol for message-orientation, queuing, routing, reliability, and security.
 - ▶ JavaScript Object Notation (**JSON**) messages, a lightweight data-interchange format. It is based on a subset of the JavaScript Programming Language Standard ECMA-262 3rd Edition - December 1999.
 - ▶ **RabbitMQ**, the most widely deployed open-source broker.
 - ▶ **Firebase**, a Cloud Messaging of google, a cross-platform messaging solution that provides a reliably send messages.
- ▶ **Communication:**
 - ▶ **REST APIs** (also known as RESTful API), application programming interface (API or web API) that conforms to the constraints of REST architectural style and allows for interaction with RESTful web services.
 - ▶ Real-time communication for the web with **WebRTC**

In sum, the ValueCare digital solution architecture will support the use of **industry standard application interfaces, or Software Development Kits**, where available for communication among the software and hardware. This supports the greatest possible interoperability with third party hardware. The architecture will support the connections between the Virtual Coach and Vidaz4 and will facilitate the integration of activity tracker device using SDK (Beurer AS 99) or using API (for Xiaomi band devices). The possibility of connecting with other third party's systems in the future will be investigated in **D3.4 ValueCare integration framework including definitions of the API FHIR** foreseen in month 30 (May 2022) and will present the procedure on how the ValueCare digital solution will be able to be interoperable with third systems. This deliverable will be deeply reviewed in the next version of this deliverable (D7.6).

WP3 – Digital IT for Value-based Integrated Care -> D3.3 Conceptual design

The aim of D3.3 is to report the structural and functional definition of the technical solution, including the mechanisms for achieving the interaction among its different components; that is, to provide the overall picture of how the different technical components of the solution, namely the ValueCare web platform, the mobile app and the virtual coach interact with each other based on the requirements identified in D3.2. For that reason, the protocols and standards mentioned in the deliverable had been already identified in the D3.2.

WP4 – ValueCare pilots' implementation -> D4.2 ValueCare Implementation plan for each pilot site

The D4.2 provides the guidelines for each pilot site based on the ValueCare general framework (D4.1) adapted to their specific target group and requirements. In this sense, the deliverable provides new information on the instruments to measure health and wellbeing outcomes in each pilot site to be added to those included in the common questionnaire developed in WP5. In this sense, pilots will use in addition:

- ▶ **Validated questionnaires available in ValueCare pilot sites national languages:**
 - ▶ GR-DMSES (Greek version of the Diabetes Management Self-Efficacy Scale) in Athens
 - ▶ RAPA 2 (Rapid Assessment of Physical Activity) questionnaire in Athens
 - ▶ PAID (Problem Areas in Diabetes Questionnaire) in Athens
 - ▶ WHO-5 (Five Wellbeing index) in Athens
 - ▶ Short Physical Performance Battery test in Valencia
 - ▶ Loneliness scale (the complete version, since the short one is already included in EMC's questionnaire) - validated in Portuguese.
 - ▶ SPMSQ (Pfeiffer questionário) for Portuguese population
 - ▶ SUS (to assess the usability of the technology) in Portugal.

- ▶ **Questionnaires already translated but not validated in pilot sites national languages:**
 - ▶ SUS (System Usability Scale) in Athens
 - ▶ MDPO 16 (Mobile Device Proficiency Questionnaire) in Athens
- ▶ **Questionnaires not available in ValueCare pilot sites national languages:**
 - ▶ ICHOM Standard Sets according to the specific chronic conditions of their target group. In particular, along the ValueCare pilot sites the following sets are being discussed at the moment of this deliverable writing among pilot sites, so authors in charge of this deliverable will be able to provide more information on the ICHOM sets used in ValueCare in further versions of this deliverable. The data sets that are being discussed now are:
 - ICHOM Stroke Set in the case of Rotterdam
 - ICHOM Diabetes set in the case of Athens
 - ▶ Protein Screener index will be translated to Spanish and used in the Valencia pilot site
 - ▶ Carlson Co-morbidity Index will be translated to Greek and used in the Athens pilot site

WP5 - Formative and summative evaluation of the VALUECARE pilot -> D5.1 Agreed-upon pilot sites evaluation framework

D5.1. establishes the evaluation framework for the ValueCare project to be implemented in a pre-post-controlled design in terms of effects for the target groups (older people, their families, and health and social professionals) at pilot sites. In this sense, the deliverable established the (self-reported) questionnaires as the tool to collect data from the three target groups. Those instruments are partly based on **the ICHOM data set for Older Person** (ICHOM, 2016; Akpan et al., 2018) and existing validated instruments to measure the variables detected in the D2.2 in the WP2. The link between both deliverables (D2.2 and D5.1), that is, the relation between the variables to be measured and the instruments included in the ValueCare questionnaires is summarised in the following table to identify the use of standard instruments in the implementation/evaluation phases of the ValueCare project (Table 2).

Variable identification (WP2)	Measurement instrument (WP5)
Activities of daily living functioning	Barthel
Frailty stage	Tilburg Frailty Indicator FRAIL scale (Valencia) Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB) (Valencia) Psychosocial motivational interview (Valencia) Protein screener (Valencia)
Falls	Falls Efficacy Scale -International (FES-I) Visual Analogue Scale for Fear of Falling (VAS FOF)
Polypharmacy	MRQ-10
Smoking status Co-morbid conditions Support b devices Shared decision making Autonomy and control Alcohol use	ICHOM older person set
Nutrition	SNAQ65+
Physical activity	IPAQ (only one item) SHARE-FRAILITY (only one item) Canada's physical activity readiness questionnaire – PAR-Q (Rijeka)* PARmed-X (Rijeka)*

Health related quality of life	PROMIS-10 global health EQ-5D-5L
Mental health	WHO-5**
Cognitive screening	Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) (Treviso)***
Happiness	Happiness scale****
Loneliness	UCLA-3-item scale
Care use	SMRC Health Care utilisation questionnaire
Care burden	4-item Zarit burden interview
Time spent in activities to care for patient	Valuation of Informal Care Questionnaire (iVICQ)
Job satisfaction	Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire
Work-related burnout	Copenhagen burnout inventory

Table 2: Validated instruments and standards used at ValueCare pilot sites to measure the needed data identified in WP2

* Rijeka decided not to include these instruments in their evaluation

** The mental health is measured with the PROMIS index in the final version of the questionnaire.

*** The MMSE is not included in the set of Treviso evaluation tools because it is used in their routine care for MCI diagnosis, but it is being used for cognitive status assessment at the Centre for Cognitive Diseases - and the results will be available for the project activities.

**** The Happiness item has been removed from the questionnaire.

D5.1 also reports on the scales used to measure the health-related quality of life, overall health, fall risk, appropriate medication use, loneliness, happiness, frailty, autonomy and control, participation in decision making, etc. The deliverable identifies some of the instruments already listed in the table 3 and adds the following (Table 3):

Target group	Variable	Measurement instrument
Older people	Health related quality of life	WHO disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHO-DAS 12)*
	Frailty	Canadian Study on health and Aging Clinical Frailty Scale*
Informal caregivers	Autonomy and control	Adult Social Care Outcomes Toolkit
Older people and professionals	Incremental quality of life years	Quality-Adjusted Life Years (QALYs)**
	Happiness	One item of the 36-Item Short Form Survey Instrument (SF-36)*
Professionals	Working conditions	Culture of Care Barometer tool
	Costs of healthcare	Productivity Cost questionnaire (PCQ)

Table 3: Validated instruments to measure variables identified in the WP5

* These instruments have been removed from the final version of questionnaire, although they are part of the ICHOM data set for older people

** This instrument has not been included in the final version of the questionnaire as from the EQ-5D-5L measures the quality of life, but only for the case of older person, not for professionals.

WP 8 - Ethics and Data Protection -> D8.7 and D8.8. Data management Plan.

The Data Management defines and monitors the data management performed within the ValueCare lifecycle and their exploitation after the project. In concrete, it defines the data to be collected in each pilot site, and how the data will be collected, processed, shared, storage, accessed and protected; but also, information about data management during and after the project, methodology and **standards to be used**, cybersecurity (in relation to WP3) access requirements, etc. In this sense, the deliverable states that the approach the project follows will privilege the adoption of **standard terminologies**

(e.g., LOINC, SNOMED) and standard **data representation and transferring format** (e.g., HL7, FHIR) were possible, to enable unambiguous data semantics and system interoperability.

HL7 International (Health Level Seven) provides a framework (and related standards) for the exchange, integration, sharing, and retrieval of electronic health information. These standards define how information is packaged and communicated from one party to another, setting the language, structure and data types required for seamless integration between systems. HL7 standards support clinical practice and the management, delivery, and evaluation of health services, and are recognised as the most used in the world. This facilitates the exchange of information between pilots and the potential exchange of data with third parties in the future (HL7, 2021).

Moreover, the ValueCare data management policy adopted has been developed to be compliant with the **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) following guidelines of the European Commission for the Horizon 2020 Programme. In relation to standards, that means that:

- ▶ Efforts are being dedicated to the adoption of **standard medical terminologies** for **findable** the representation of the data, where possible (i.e., clinical parameters produced in healthcare organisations or by personal devices). If it is not possible, partners try to define **custom metadata sets and naming conventions** in order that data are searchable and can be identified without ambiguities.
- ▶ Data collected in the ValueCare platform will be **interoperable** in two ways: (i) The adherence to **standard medical terminology** (e.g., LOINC, Snomed) in the case of Clinical data produced in the healthcare organisations or by measuring devices; and (ii) The provision of adequate documentation on the data syntax and semantics in the form of **customary vocabularies and ontologies**, for those data that cannot be referred to a standard terminology (e.g., diet, physical activity).
- ▶ Moreover, some pilot sites are also working in a broad level to the interoperability of their systems as it is the case of Treviso where local health authorities are called to meet the interoperability standards of data to respond to the Regional Health Record requirements.

In general terms, ValueCare project is adopting standard data representation format to make data both interoperable and **reusable**.

In this sense, next versions of the deliverable on Data Management should be analysed to explore how data produced and/or used in the project will be identified and located in standards identification mechanisms or the need to create new standards.

4.2 Existing common standards

In this section, the preliminary analysis of common existing standards in the health and social care and data (in both domains) is presented. Those standards focused on images and related information has not been considered as they are out of the scope of the ValueCare project. Technological partners will include their inputs in further versions of this deliverable.

4.2.1 Existing common standards in health and social care

In this first version of the deliverable, authors have focused on the ICHOM data set included in the ValueCare approach. ICHOM was founded in 2012 by Professor Michael Porter of Harvard Business School, Martin Ingvar of the Karolinska Institute, and the Boston Consulting Group. ICHOM's mission is to unlock the potential of value-based health care by defining global Standard Sets of outcome measures that really matter to patients for the most relevant medical conditions and by driving adoption and reporting of these measures worldwide.

ICHOM Standard Sets are standardised outcomes, measurement tools and time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition (i.e., older person). By creating a standardised list of the outcomes based on the patient's priorities along with instruments and time points for measurement,

ICHOM ensure the patient remains at the centre of their care. To date, ICHOM has published 39 Standard Sets covering different conditions and for specific patient populations.

In ValueCare, all pilot sites will use the **ICHOM Standard Set for Older Person** composed by the following domains together with some demographic and clinical factors (Table 4):

Domain	Measure	Supporting information
Demographic factors	Age	Date of birth
	Sex	Sex at birth
	Ethnicity	Determined by country
	Level of education	Highest level of education
	Living status and location	Most recent living arrangements
	Smoking status	Smoking status
	Alcohol use	Alcohol consumed regularly
	Body mass index	Body mass index
Clinical factors	Frailty stage	Canadian Study on Health Ageing Clinical Frailty Scale
	Inappropriate medication use	Antipsychotics, benzodiazepines, tricyclic antidepressants, opioids, 1st generation antihistamines, vasodilators or antispasmodics have been prescribed in the previous 12 months
	Cognitive impairment	If any cognitive impairment exists
	Comorbidities	Comorbidities include heart disease, high blood pressure, lung disease, diabetes, kidney disease, liver disease, disease of the nervous system, cancer (within the past 5 years), depression, substance abuse, high cholesterol
	Activities of daily living	Barthel
	Nº of medications prescribed	Total number of medications prescribed
	Hearing or vision impairment	If any hearing or vision impairment exists
	Level of care received	Frequency of support at home, if any
	Disutility of Care	Polypharmacy
Falls		Nº of falls in the last 12 months Nº of falls that resulted in a fracture, need of medical attention, need of hospitalisation
Symptoms, functioning, quality of life	Autonomy and control	Adult Social Care Outcomes Toolkit
	Mood and emotional health	SF-36
	Pain	

	<u>Activities of daily living</u>	SF-36 and gait speed
	<u>Loneliness and isolation</u>	<u>UCLA 3 item scale</u>
Care	<u>Care burden</u>	<u>Zarit 4 item</u>
Healthcare responsiveness	Participation and decision making	Confidence, ability to cope with own health, role as participant in care...
Clinical Status	<u>Frailty</u>	Canadian Study on Health Ageing Clinical Frailty Scale
	<u>Time spent in hospital</u>	Nº of hospital admissions, readmission and time spent in hospital over a year
	Overall cause-specific survival	All-cause survival
Quality of Death	Place of death	Whether a preferred place to die expressed

Table 4: ICHOM data set for older person domains and relation with the ValueCare questionnaire for older person

The domains highlighted **in blue** are considered in the ValueCare questionnaire. Moreover, some measures are considered using different questionnaires (those highlighted in **orange**), for example, the hearing and vision impairments are considered as part of the Tilburg questionnaire; the number of medications prescribed is measured in the ValueCare questionnaire with the “medication Risk Questionnaire – MRQ-10”. These adaptations had been made based on the comments made by the consortium and resulted in a combination of the ICHOM data set for older person and overall adult health set.

Figure 1: ICHOM data set for older person

4.2.2 Existing common data standards on health

Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP)

The OMOP Common Data Model allows systematic analysis of databases transforming data contained in these databases into a common format (data model), common representation (terminologies, vocabularies, coding schemes) and then conduct analysis using a library of standard analytic routines that have been written in the common format¹. Once a database has been converted to the OMOP Common Data Model evidence can be generated using standardised analytics tools.

In this framework, the **project EHDEN**² (European health data and evidence network) aims to collaborate with European institutions and data sources to harmonising data to the OMOP Common

¹ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/the-common-data-model/>

² <https://www.ehden.eu/datapartners/>

Data Model through a federated network. **EMC leads the project and ICHOM is partner of the consortium.**

Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)

FHIR is a standard for health care data exchange published by HL7³. FHIR is designed to enable information exchange to support the provision of healthcare in a wide variety of settings. The specification builds on and adapts modern practices to enable the provision of integrated healthcare across a wide range of teams and organisations. The intended scope of FHIR is broad, covering human and veterinary, clinical care, public health, clinical trials, administration, and financial aspects. The standard is intended for global use and in a wide variety of architectures and scenarios. It was already mentioned because it was included in the analysed deliverables from the WP8. **Among ValueCare partners, Athens, and Treviso use HL7.**

Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC)

LOINC are the international standards for identifying health measurements, observations and documents grown in Indiana, USA, but with worldwide users. LOINC provides universal codes and names that provide the global lingua franca for identifying tests and observations. So, LOINC is a common language and a common catalogue of measurements including laboratory tests, clinical measures, standardises survey instruments and more. It enables the exchange and aggregation of clinical results for care delivery, outcomes management and research⁴.

Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine (SNOMED)

SNOMED International is a not-for-profit organization that owns, administers, and develops SNOMED CT, the world's most comprehensive clinical terminology. With SNOMED CT users can record patient data more accurately and comprehensively and use tools and analytics to provide better patient care and health management.

HL7 and SNOMED had subscribed different collaboration agreements aimed at improving interoperability among both standards, focusing on the adoption of working practices that facilitate the use of SNOMED with HL7 standards globally. In the same line, LOINC and SNOMED CT signed a long-term agreement aimed to improve safety, functionality, and interoperability for the number of clinicians who manage and exchange health data with electronic medical records.

Sentinel Common Data Model (SCDM)

The Sentinel Operations Centre (SOC) coordinates the network of Sentinel Data Partners and leads development of the Sentinel Common Data Model (SCDM), a standard data structure that allows Data Partners to quickly execute distributed programs against local data with administrative data, clinical data, registry data, inpatients data, mother-infants linkage data and auxiliar data⁵.

4.2.3 Existing common standards at technological level applied to ValueCare digital solution

Technological partners will include the standards applied in the final version of this deliverable.

³ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/>

⁴ <https://loinc.org/about/>

⁵ <https://www.sentinelinitiative.org/methods-data-tools/sentinel-common-data-model>

4.3 Standardisation committees and related organisations

In this section, the first mapping exercise to identify European standardisation committees and national committees and related organisations from the countries of the ValueCare consortium is presented.

4.3.1 Standardisation bodies at EU level

Overview of the main standardisation bodies at EU level:

- **International Organization for Standardization (ISO)** - Gathers 166 national standardisation bodies, with one representative per country, covering all economic activity, except for electrical engineering and telecommunications. Among them: medical devices, health organisation management (general requirements for telehealth management), health care quality management system standard, etc. To get involved or create synergies, the national members should be contacted.
- **International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)** - Organisation of 75 members that prepares and publishes international standards for all electrical, electronic and related technologies, operating in the field of electrical engineering, thus complementing the scope of ISO. Among them, electrical equipment in medical practice, common aspects of electrical equipment used in medical practice, etc. Different contacts can be extracted from this link: <https://www.iec.ch/iec-directory>
- **Comité Européen de Normalisation [European Committee for Standardization] (CEN)** - promotes the voluntary harmonisation of technical standards in Europe, designated as "EN", in several domains, among them health and safety and healthcare. Contacts for the health domain: cvigneron@cencenelec.eu; jogbonna@cencenelec.eu
- **Comité Européen de Normalisation Electrotechnique [European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization] (CENELEC)** - draws voluntary electrotechnical standards, contributing to the development of electrical and electrotechnical goods and services. It brings together 34 European national electrotechnical committees. Again, here there is domain on occupational health and safety.
- **European Telecommunications Standard Institute (ETSI)** - produces globally applicable standards for Information and Communication Technologies, including fixed, mobile, radio, convergent, broadcast and internet technologies. Among their sectors it is included eHealth.

Outside Europe, one of the pilot sites (Treviso) mentioned the **Qmentum Accreditation Canada (international level)**⁶ performed by the Accreditation Canada Team. This programme is designed to focus on quality and safety throughout all aspects of an organisation's services—from governance and leadership to direct care and infrastructure—to the benefit of patients, clients, residents, staff and volunteers. Qmentum follows a process like the Institutional accreditation, but it uses a broader range of standards and offers a more in-depth assessment. It uses evidence-informed standards developed by Health Standards Organization (HSO). There are four sets of standards at the core of the program: (i) Governance; (ii) Leadership; (iii) Infection Prevention and Control; (iv) Medication Management. **AULSS2 currently uses the results and methodology to guide ongoing quality improvement activities.** Qmentum accreditation can be applied at the national, system or provider level – helping organization to measure and improve quality using common standards and language to increase efficiency, communication, and coordination.

⁶ <https://accreditation.ca/qmentum-accreditation/>

4.3.2 Standardisation bodies at National level

Athens - Greek level

ELOT- Hellenic Body for Standardisation <http://www.elot.gr/>

In Greece, ELOT is the sole national body responsible for the elaboration, approval, publication and distribution of Hellenic Standards. The elaboration of Standards is entrusted to ELOT's Technical Committees and Working Groups, in which interested parties from both the Public and the Private Sector are represented, to achieve maximum possible consensus among them. In this framework, ELOT operates more than 190 Technical Committees and Working Groups, members of which are more than 1100 distinguished Greek scientists.

Health care	Socio-sanitary	Generic certifications also applicable to health and social care
EN 15224 is a specialized standard that concerns application of a quality management system in the healthcare sector ISO 15189 Medical Laboratory Accreditation	UNE 15224 Health Care Services	Quality ISO 9001 Quality management Assessment EFQM Security ISO 45001 Health and Safety at Work UNE 171330-2 Indoor air quality ISO 27001 and ISO 27701 Information Security ISO 22000 Food Safety Environment ISO 14001 Environmental management

Table 5: ELOT certifications applied to health and social care

ELOT's certificates are intended for both **public and private organisations**: from health services or health councils in all autonomous communities to hospitals, clinics, haemodialysis centres, image diagnosis centres, laboratories.

CONTACT: info@elot.gr

Coimbra - Portugal level

IPQ – Instituto Português da Qualidade [Portuguese Institute for Quality] <http://www1.ipq.pt/PT/Pages/Homepage.aspx>

The **Portuguese Institute for Quality** (IPQ) is a public entity aimed at carrying out the standardisation process at the national level. It has the mission of coordinating the Portuguese quality system, promoting activities that contribute to demonstrate the credibility of the action of economic agents, as also developing activities necessary for its functions as a National Metrology Institution and as a National Standards Organization. Under the latest, IPQ promotes the preparation of Portuguese standards, ensuring their consistency and update, as well as the adjustment of national legislation on products to the standards of the European Union.

Additionally, at an international level, the IPQ monitors and implements community directives, participates in European standardisation processes, and recognises qualification of notified bodies. It represents Portugal, as a member in several International and European Organisations for Standardisation relevant to its mission.

At a more specific level, the IPQ coordinate Sectoral Bodies – that may be public, private or mixed bodies - to carry out standardisation activities in a given domain. These Technical Commissions prepare standardisation plans, disseminate the normative activity of and carry out normative clarifications on the areas of their sector. Particularly, in regard to the field of health/social care, the following shall be mentioned:

Technical Commission/ SECTORAL BODY	AREA of INTERVENTION
Agência Nacional para a Inovação (ANI) [National Agency for Innovation]	Research, Development and Innovation
Associação Portuguesa de Ética Empresarial (APEE) [Portuguese Association of Business Ethics]	Ethics and social responsibility
Associação Portuguesa de Gestão de Projetos (APOGEP) [Portuguese Association of Project Management]	Project management
Associação Portuguesa das Empresas de Dispositivos Médicos (APORMED) [Portuguese Association of Medical Device Companies]	Health Technology
Associação Portuguesa para a Qualidade [Portuguese Association for Quality]	Quality management and quality assurance; Accreditation; Risk Management; societal safety
Associação Portuguesa de Segurança Electrónica e de Protecção Incêndio (APSEI) [Portuguese Association for Safety]	Safety and Health at Work

Table 6: technical commissions working in the health and social care

Regarding the certification/standardisation services provided by the IPQ in the health/social care field, the following shall be mentioned:

HEALTH CARE	SOCIO-SANITARY	GENERIC CERTIFICATIONS ALSO APPLICABLE TO HEALTH AND SOCIAL CARE
<u>Hygienic Masks</u> <u>UNE 15224</u> Health Care Services <u>UNE 179003</u> Risk management for Patient safety <u>UNE 179006</u> Surveillance, prevention and control of health care-associated infections <u>UNE 179007</u> Quality management system for assisted reproductive laboratories <u>UNE 179008</u> Liver transplant unit <u>UNE 179001</u> Dental services <u>UNE 179002</u> Medical transport <u>ISO 13485</u> Healthcare products	<u>UNE 15224</u> Health Care Services <u>UNE 158000</u> Social services <u>UNE 179003</u> Risk management for Patient safety	<u>ISO 9001</u> Quality management Assessment <u>EFQM</u> Health and Safety at Work <u>ISO 45001</u> Health and Safety at Work <u>UNE 171330-2</u> Indoor air quality <u>ISO 27001</u> and <u>ISO 27701</u> Information Security <u>ISO 22000</u> Food Safety Environment <u>ISO 14001</u> Environmental management <u>Zero waste</u> Social responsibility <u>UNE 170001</u> Universal accessibility management <u>IQNet SR10</u> Social responsibility management <u>Healthy organisation</u> R&D&i <u>UNE 166002</u> R+D+i m

Table 7: IPQ certifications applied to health and social care

The Portuguese Institute for Quality (IPQ) can perform: (i) Accreditation (formal recognition of the competence of an entity to carry out a certain activity) - to laboratories, inspection entities, certifying entities; and (ii) Certification (credible confirmation of compliance to the requirements specified in

reference documents) - of public or private organisations, products, processes, services or people. Therefore, IPQ's standards shall guide social and health care organisations, services and providers.

CONTACT: ipq@ipq.pt

Cork/Kerry - Ireland level

NSAI - National Standards Authority of Ireland

[https://shop.standards.ie/#:~:text=NSAI%20\(National%20Standards%20Authority%20of, is%20Ireland's%20official%20standards%20body.](https://shop.standards.ie/#:~:text=NSAI%20(National%20Standards%20Authority%20of, is%20Ireland's%20official%20standards%20body.)

The National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI) is the Ireland's official standards body. They operate under the National Standards Authority of Ireland Act (1996) and are accountable to the Minister for Business, Employment and Retail. As Ireland's Official standards body, NSAI aims to inspire consumer confidence and create the infrastructure for products and services to be recognised and relied on, all over the world.

HIQA - The Health Information and Quality Authority - www.hiqa.ie

The Health Information and Quality Authority (HIQA) is an independent authority established to drive high-quality and safe care for people using our health and social care services in Ireland.

Health care	Socio-sanitary	Generic certifications also applicable to health and social care
Medical Device Management Systems ISO 13485 CEN/TC 205 – Non- active medical devices Health Informatics Standards ISO TC 215 and CEN TC 251 HIQA National Standards for Residential Care Settings for Older People in Ireland. HIQA National Standards for the Conduct of Reviews of Patient Safety Incidents HIQA National Standards for the prevention and control of healthcare-associated infections in acute healthcare services HIQA National Standards for the prevention and control of healthcare-associated infections in acute healthcare services	HIQA National Standards for Safer Better Healthcare HIQA National Standards for Adult Safeguarding HIQA Supporting people's autonomy guidelines HIQA Guidance on a Human Rights-based Approach in Health and Social Care Services	Quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Quality Management Systems ISO 9001 – Excellence Through People Scheme 1000:2017] Security <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ISO/IEC 27001 Information Security Management System – ISO 45001 Occupational Health & Safety Management Environment: Environmental Management Systems ISO 14001 Social responsibility: SA8000 Social Responsibility

Table 8: Certifications applied to health and social care

Where a standard already exists, NSAI works with businesses to help them apply it. Where a standard may be needed, NSAI will work with relevant parties at national or international level to create and

develop the appropriate standard. NSAI improves the performance of Irish business and protects consumers through the setting of standards and issuing of certification in the quality and safety of goods and services. From other side, HIQA's mandate to date extends across a specified range of public, private and voluntary sector services. Reporting to the Minister for Health and engaging with the Minister for Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth Affairs, HIQA's role is to develop standards, inspect and review

CONTACT NSAI: info@nsai.ie

CONTACT HIQA: info@hiqa.ie

Rijeka - Croatia level

Croatian Standards Institute <https://www.hzn.hr/default.aspx?id=6>

The Croatian Standards Institute is an independent and non-profit public institution established as a national standardisation body of the Republic of Croatia in order to achieve the goals of standardization.

Agency for Quality and Accreditation in Health and Social Welfare
<https://www.aaz.hr/hr/kvaliteta/standardi>

The Agency for Quality and Accreditation in Health and Social Welfare is a legal entity with competence in the field of ensuring and improving the quality of health care, accreditation in health care and health technology assessment processes, and in the field of ensuring and improving the quality of social services and accreditation of social welfare providers. on the quality of health care

Croatian Accreditation Agency <https://akreditacija.hr/en/about-us/>

Croatian Accreditation Agency is an independent and non for-profit public institution that acts as the national accreditation service in the Republic of Croatia.

Health care	Socio-sanitary	Generic certifications also applicable to health and social care
<p>EN ISO 9001:2015 Quality management systems for healthcare EN 15224 :201</p> <p>HRN EN ISO 9004:2018 Quality management – Quality of an organization – Guidance to achieve sustained success</p> <p>HRI CEN/TR 15592:2008 Health services -Quality management systems -Guide for the use of EN ISO 9004:2000 in health services for performance improvement (CEN/TR 15592:2007)</p> <p>HRN EN 17398:2020 Patient involvement in health care -- Minimum requirements for person-centred care (EN 17398:2020)</p> <p>CWA 17553:2020, Community face coverings – Guide to minimum requirements, methods of testing and use</p>	<p>ISO 14001 environmental management system</p> <p>EN ISO 22000:2018 Food safety management systems – Requirements for any organization in the food chain</p> <p>HRS ISO/TS 22002 Prerequisite programmes on food safety</p>	<p>Quality</p> <p>EN ISO 9001:2015 Quality management system for healthcare (EN 15224:2016)</p> <p>HRN EN ISO 9004:2018 Quality management – Quality of an organization – Guidance to achieve sustained success</p> <p>EN ISO 9004:2000 Health services -- Quality management systems -- Guide for the use of in health services for performance improvement (CEN/TR 15592:2007)</p> <p>Security</p> <p>HRN EN ISO 22000:2018 Food safety management</p> <p>Environment</p> <p>ISO 14001</p> <p>Social responsibility</p> <p>HRN EN 17398:2020 Patient involvement in health care- Minimum requirements for person-centred care (EN 17398:2020)</p>

Table 9: existing standardisation applied to health and social care

In accordance with the Standardization Act and the Regulation on the Establishment of the Croatian Standards Institute, a part of HZN's activities comprise tasks which are of interest for the Republic of Croatia. The aims of standardization are as follows: to make a product, process or service fit for its purpose, controlling variety by using the optimum number of types or sizes, ensuring compatibility of various products, health, safety, protection of the environment, etc. They are intended for both, **private and public organizations**. Technical regulation prescribes the safety of products and free movement of goods on the internal market, citizens' health protection, consumers' protection, environment protection and other relevant public interest areas.

CONTACT: normoteka@hzn.hr; akreditacija@akreditacija.hr

Rotterdam - The Netherlands level

NEN – Stichting Koninklijk Nederlands Normalisatie Instituut [the Royal Netherlands Standardization Institute] <https://www.nen.nl/en/>

NEN connects parties and stakeholders and ensure that they reach agreements in standards and guidelines. They do this in national and / or international standards committees, and manages over 31.000 standards. These standards are international (ISO, IEC), European (EN) and national (NEN) standards accepted in The Netherlands. In total, over 800 standards committees are active, with in total over 5.000 standard committee members.

Zorginstituut [the National Health Care Institute] <https://english.zorginstituutnederland.nl/about-us>

The National Health Care Institute carries out tasks relating to two Dutch statutory health insurance schemes: the Health Insurance Act (Zorgverzekeringswet) and the Long-Term Care Act (Wet langdurige Zorg, Wlz). All activities undertaken by Zorginstituut Nederland focus on making sure that everyone in the Netherlands receives good care; no more and no less than necessary.

Nictiz <https://www.nictiz.nl/english/>

It is the Dutch competence centre for electronic exchange of health and care information. Nictiz develops and manages standards that enable electronic information exchange. It ensures that healthcare information can be recorded and exchanged unambiguously. It also collects and share knowledge on electronic information exchange in healthcare, focusing not only on the Netherlands, but on international developments as well. Nictiz is a foundation with an independent Supervisory Board and funded almost entirely by the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport. Nictiz is the independent party bringing together healthcare institutions, umbrella organisations, IT suppliers and the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport.

Health care
HKZ-keurmerk
NEN7510 (information security in healthcare)
NEN7511
NEN7512
NEN7513
NEN-EN 15224
NTA7516
NIAZ Qmentum (accreditation of hospitals)
5 information standards in the field of care and support: iWlz, iWmo, iJw, iPgb, iEB

Table 10: NEN certifications applied to health and social care

NEN supports the standardisation process in The Netherlands. If a party asks NEN to affect an agreement, they start by investigating to what extent standardisation is possible, and if there is an interest in this. Then, they invite all interested parties to participate. The fields of work are: occupational health and safety, construction, consumer issues, energy & distribution, ICT, installations, agriculture & food, mechanical engineering & process installations, management systems, environment, medical care & well-being.

CONTACT NEN: klantenservice@nen.nl

The National Health Care Institute is an advisory and implementing organisation for two statutory health insurance schemes, as mentuoend, the Health Insurance Act (Zorgverzekeringswet, Zvw) and the Long-Term Care Act (Wet Langdurige Zorg, Wlz). All activities undertaken by Zorginstituut Nederland focus on making sure that everyone in the Netherlands receives good care; no more and no less than necessary.

CONTACT the National Health Care Institute:

PO Box 320, 1110 AH Diemen, The Netherlands

Office address, Willem Dudokhof 1, 1112 ZA Diemen (The Netherlands).

CONTACT NICTIZ: internationaal@nictiz.nl

Treviso - Italy level

Quality Office at AULSS2

AULSS2 has a specific structure for Quality Management with a broad experience in the certification process of the management systems related to quality of care. The Quality Office works jointly with the Risk Management, Internal Auditing and Innovation and Development structures. They also manage the accreditation pathways for specific certifications such as

Health care
Fact Net-Cord (Cord Blood Bank)
Fact-Jacie (Hematopoietic Cellular Therapy Product Collection, Processing, and Administration) and EFI (immunogenetics lab standards)
ISO 13485 (medical devices)
ISO 9001 (Quality System Management)
ISO 15189 (Laboratory Medicine)

Table 11: AULSS2 certifications

They collaborate with Veneto Region for the institutional accreditation.

Regione del Veneto - Veneto Region www.regione.veneto.it

Veneto Region is the main accreditation entity AULSS2 and other health and social authorities refers to. It develops accreditation programs according to Regional Law 22/2002 for the local health and social care provided by AULSS2 through the schedule and execution of official audits to obtain the required authorisation to provide health and social services.

Laboratorio MeS – MeS Laboratory University of Pisa

Since 2012 the Veneto Region has joined the performance evaluation system of regional health systems, designed by Management and Health Laboratory of the Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies in Pisa. Such system provides a measurement mode and representation of performances of Health authorities through the so called "On target" scheme, which offers an intuitive picture summary of the performance obtained, illustrating its strengths immediately points of weakness to regional and local health authorities.

The indicators evaluated are almost 300 related to the different company dimensions: the state of health of the population, the ability to pursue regional strategies, the evaluation of the economic and financial dynamics and operational efficiency, evaluation the experience of users and employees, the area of Emergency-Urgency, collective prevention, governance and quality of the offer, pharmaceutical assistance. With regard to the National Outcome Plan, which evaluates effectiveness, fairness, safety and the appropriateness of the treatments produced in the context of hospital care, hospitals of the Local Health Authority n. 2 have achieved a very high level of performance on most of the main indicators. MeS provides guidance to implement PROMs and PREMs and also to drive an assessment of corporate wellbeing to reduce work-related stressors and enhance work environment.

CONTACT: ids@santannapisa.it

Valencia - Spanish level

AENOR - Asociación Española de Normalización y Certificación [Spanish Association for Normalisation and Certification] <https://www.en.aenor.com/>

The entity provides services for conformity assessment (certification, inspection and testing), training and information. AENOR's certifications range from management systems to products. In the **health and social sector**, AENOR has developed a broad catalogue of certifications that contribute to improving health services management and the satisfaction of all users of the system:

Health care	Socio-sanitary	Generic certifications also applicable to health and social care
Hygienic Masks UNE 15224 Health Care Services UNE 179003 Risk management for Patient safety UNE 179006 Surveillance, prevention and control of health care-associated infections UNE 179007 Quality management system for assisted reproductive laboratories UNE 179008 Liver transplant unit UNE 179001 Dental services UNE 179002 Medical transport ISO 13485 Health care products	UNE 15224 Health Care Services UNE 158000 Social services UNE 179003 Risk management for Patient safety	Quality ISO 9001 Quality management Assessment EFQM Security ISO 45001 Health and Safety at Work UNE 171330-2 Indoor air quality ISO 27001 and ISO 27701 Information Security ISO 22000 Food Safety Environment ISO 14001 Environmental management Zero waste Social responsibility UNE 170001 Universal accessibility management IQNet SR10 Social responsibility management Healthy organisation R&D&i UNE 166002 R+D+i management

Table 12: AENOR certifications applied to health and social care

AENOR's certificates are intended for both **public and private organisations**: from health services or health councils in all autonomous communities to hospitals, clinics, haemodialysis centres, image diagnosis centres, laboratories, or sanitary transportation companies, along with opticians, pharmacies, dentists, and all kinds of centres that provide socio-sanitary services, such as residences, day/night centres, etc.

CONTACT: info@aenor.com

4.4 Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from the results of the project (Subtask 7.5.2).

ValueCare is contributing to new standards developments in specific topics related to the objectives of the project, in particular to the **ICHOMs set of outcomes** with:

- ▶ (i) the involvement of Mona Khalid, representative of this relevant organisation as chair of the ValueCare Advisory Board. In the coming meetings of the Advisory Board, standardisation will be also a topic to be discussed; and
- ▶ (ii) the inclusion of the ICHOM data set of older people in the ValueCare questionnaires to be implemented in the 7 pilot sites. This was already mentioned in previous section as well as the potential use of other ICHOM data sets in concrete pilot sites according to the target populations.

Moreover, the ValueCare questionnaires entail a comprehensive set of instruments (already detailed in previous section). Some of them are not available in the ValueCare national languages so pilots are, at the time of this deliverable, translating these instruments for which no validated translations are available (forward and backward translations). The instruments translations are discussed by the study team and adapted when needed. This is the case of the instruments detailed in the following table (Table 11). In some cases where no validated translations were available, partners used the translated versions used in previous projects. That is the case of some items of the Spanish questionnaire, where Valencia pilot side used the same adaptation of a previous project (UHCE) where EMC and UVEG were involved (also reported in Table 11).

QUESTIONNAIRES	Greece	Portugal	Croatia	The Netherlands	Italy	Spain
PROMIS-10	✓	Already validated	✓	Already validated	✓	Already validated
EQ-5D-5L	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated
Tilburg Frailty Index	Translated but not validated previously	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated
ICHOM older person set	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UCLA 3-item loneliness scale	Already validated	Already validated	Translated but not validated previously	✓	Already validated	✓
Barthel	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	✓	Already validated	Already validated
Visual Analogue Scale for Fear of Falling (VAS-FOF)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Falls Efficacy Scale-International (FES-I)	Already validated	Already validated	✓	✓	✓	Translated but not validated previously
SNAQ65+	✓	Translated but not validated previously	✓	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated
MRQ-10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Already validated
SMRC Health Care utilization questionnaire	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
iMTA Productivity Cost Questionnaire	✓	Translated but not validated previously	✓	✓	✓	✓
iMTA Valuation of Informal Care Questionnaire	✓	✓	✓	Already validated	✓	Translated but not validated previously
ZARIT Burden	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	✓	Already validated	Already validated
Culture of Care Barometer Tool	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire	Already validated	Already validated	✓	✓	✓	Translated but not validated previously
Copenhagen Burnout Inventory	Already validated	Already validated	✓	✓	Already validated	Already validated

International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ)	Already validated	Already validated	Already validated	✓	Already validated	Already validated
SHARE-Frailty	✓	✓	✓	✓	Already validated	✓

Table 13: Translated versions of validated instruments to be used during the ValueCare implementation phase.

Some partners have the intention to publish the use of translated versions in scientific journals and then, contribute to their validation. So, it will be monitored and reported in the next version of this deliverable in month 54.

5 Roadmap towards standardisation

As mentioned in the section 2.1 of this D7.5, one of the specific objectives of the task 7.5 is to use the standardisation system as a tool for dissemination of the project results and interaction with the market stakeholders. For that reason, the subtask 7.5.2. is addressed to analyse the contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from the results of the project, including the collaboration with the relevant standardisation Technical Committees. In addition to the work done in this task so far, as following the recommendations made by the reviewers, a first overview of the **roadmap towards standardisation** to be followed during the coming months is defined in this section.

OBJECTIVE: to use the standardisation system as a tool for disseminate the ValueCare results and interaction with the market stakeholders. In this sense, the roadmap should seek the following:

- ▶ **Contribute to existing standards at EU and national level** -> for this, partners have already identified common standards in health and social care and data standards on health and will continue mapping them together with the analysis of existing standards at technological level (see section 4.2 of this deliverable). For those aligned with the ValueCare, partners should explore how they are contributing in terms of validation, improvement, translation, modernisation, barriers for implementation, etc. and reporting them about the achieved results to generate synergies and real impact on these standards with potential changes, validation in different languages/contexts, introduction of agile methods, etc.
- ▶ **Networking activities with related standardisation technical committees** -> some of them at national and EU level had already been identified in this deliverable (see section 4.3). Once recognised the potential contribution of ValueCare to existing standards, partners can detect standardisation priorities, bottlenecks, and facilitators to be discussed with the main standardisation committees identified at European and national level in work with them in delivering/improving coordination, efficiency, and flexibility in European/national standards.
- ▶ **Contribute with a more coordinated and updated approach to health and health data standards** in Europe, considering the needs of older people with different profiles (cognitive impairment, frailty, and multiple chronic conditions) and their care team (formal and informal) in an integrated and efficient outcome-based care.

ACTIONS:

- ▶ Continue with the mapping exercise: health standards, health data standards and technological standards applicable to the ValueCare digital solution.
- ▶ Explore how ValueCare can contribute to these standards: KVC with the support of EMC will propose some ideas from health standards approach, WP8 partners will propose some ideas from the health data perspective, and technological partners will propose some ideas from the technological part to be discussed in an internal webinar with the whole consortium. Then the ideas will be analysed and structured in practical contributions by KVC and agreed by the whole consortium.
- ▶ Consultation with AB and relevant stakeholders at European and national level about the ideas arisen from the internal webinar.
- ▶ Schedule meetings with standardisation bodies based on the ideas collected in the webinar and finally agreed by ValueCare partners. KVC will provide some tips for the meetings and conduct the meetings at European level and pilot sites will do the same at national level.
- ▶ Report about the ValueCare contribution to standards in a practical and editable format and disseminate it with the support of IFIC to the relevant audiences.

In all these activities, partners will engage the Advisory Board as key actor, in particular the chair of the board because of her relationship with ICHOM datasets.

TIMELINE:

	2022		2023		2024	
	January- June	July- December	January- June	July- December	January- April	May
Mapping exercise						
Analysis on how ValueCare can contribute to standards		Webinar	Consultation			
Meetings with standardisation bodies						
Working on the report and its dissemination						Submission of the D7.6

6 Findings and conclusions

The **main objective** of the task 7.5 “Standardisation activities” is to facilitate the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the ValueCare developed solutions. In this line, **two specific objectives** were identified:

- To provide starting information for other WPs, ensure compatibility and interoperability with what already exists in the market through standards.
- To use the standardisation system as a tool for dissemination of the project results and interaction with the market stakeholders.

To respond to the above two specific objectives, two task has been developed under the task 7.5 whose main preliminary results has been presented in this deliverable:

1. Identification and analysis of related existing standards

As a first step, this deliverable presents an analysis of the already submitted deliverables to detect any standardisation implication and needs along the ValueCare WPs, together with a mapping of European and national standardisation bodies and exiting standards applicable to ValueCare.

2. Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from the results of the project, including the collaboration with relevant standardisation Technical Committees

As a result of previous task, partners have compiled a first comprehensive list of national and international standardisation bodies that can be engaged in the ValueCare project activities (exploitation activities in particular). Moreover, the contribution to ValueCare to existing evaluation questionnaires has been analysed in relation to the WP5 on evaluation.

From previous tasks, the following **conclusions** can be summarised:

- A further exploration should be done with the **definitive versions** of some of the already analysed deliverables (as the D2.2.) as they are preliminary versions, so the information can be modified according to the project needs.
- Some **validated indexes** will be used in the ValueCare evaluation (WP5) for the clinical information. These indexes had previously been validated, but not in all the partners languages and contexts, so the potential contribution of ValueCare to their validation is explored in this deliverable and will be further analysed in the next versions of this deliverable. In this sense, it is important to mention that all pilot sites will implement the ValueCare questionnaire designed by EMC for older people, informal caregivers, and health and social professionals, and some pilots will also implement additional questionnaires to measure specific conditions of their target population that they need to adapt and personalise the integrate care pathway. Also, it is important to highlight the contribution of the ValueCare to the ICHOM data set, in particular, to the ICHOM data set on older person that will be implemented (partially) by the 7 ValueCare pilot sites. In this sense, the ICHOM data set for older person is not used as a whole in the ValueCare questionnaire; so this should be reported as a **limitation** for their potential validation among ValueCare pilot sites, as only part of the domains is considered as in the ICHOM data set, other domains are measured with different instruments that those included in the ICHOM data set, and some domains are not included in the ValueCare questionnaire.
- The **technological solution** of ValueCare is also linked with the use of common standards to allow their integration with existing systems, data collection, etc. Some common components had been listed in this deliverable and a section on common standards for the ValueCare app, dashboard and virtual coach is foreseen in the next version of this deliverable.
- The ValueCare data management policy has been developed to be compliant with **FAIR principles**. In relation to standards, that implies: (i) the adoption of standard medical terminologies, (ii) the use of customary vocabularies and ontologies, and moreover (iii) some pilots are exploring the interoperability with their systems.

- Existing **common standards on health data** had been mapped and their use among ValueCare partners and pilot sites identified in this deliverable. Further analysis on how ValueCare can contribute to them will be done in the next version of this deliverable.
- **Standardisation bodies at European and national level** (considering the countries of the ValueCare consortium) has been mapped as an initial step to further engage them in concrete activities to be performed during the coming months.
- Only Athens and Coimbra considers among the questionnaires items to measure the **acceptancy of the technological solution** among the target groups. This is a potential limitation for the ValueCare study that should be considered among pilot sites and EMC as leader of the WP5 on evaluation.

Further steps in both tasks are identified in the methodology section (networking activities, to increase the mapping exercise, etc.) that will be performed during the next months of the project to present the final version of this deliverable at the end of the project. A concrete roadmap for standardisation has been outlined in section 5 and will be followed and adapted/improved according to the project tasks if needed during coming months.

7 References

Akpan, A., Roberts, C., Bandeen-Roche, K., Batty, B., Bausewein, C., Bell, D., Bramley, D., Bynum, J., Cameron, I. D., Chen, L. K., Ekdahl, A., Fertig, A., Gentry, T., Harkes, M., Haslehurst, D., Hope, J., Hurtado, D. R., Lyndon, H., Lynn, J., Martin, M., ... Banerjee, J. (2018). Standard set of health outcome measures for older persons. *BMC geriatrics*, 18(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-017-0701-3>

Council of Europe (2014). Recomendación CM/Rec (2014)2 del Comité de Ministros a los Estados miembros sobre la promoción de los derechos humanos de las personas mayores. Retrieved from: <https://goo.gl/xFDLwR>

HL7 (2021). Introduction to HL7 Standards. Retrieved from: <https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/index.cfm?ref=nav>

ICHOM (2016). Elderly Standard Set. Retrieved June 5, 2020, from: www.ichom.org

International Longevity Centre Brazil (2015). Active Ageing: A Policy Framework in Response to the Longevity Revolution. Rio de Janeiro: ILCB. Retrieved from: <https://goo.gl/YfVQUH>

Shilton, T., Sparks, M., McQueen, D., Lamarre, M. C., Jackson, S., & executive committee of the International Union for Health Promotion and Education-IUHPE (2011). Proposal for new definition of health. *BMJ (Clinical research ed.)*, 343, d5359. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d5359>

WHO (2002). Active Ageing: A Policy Framework. Geneva: World Health Organization. Retrieved from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/67215/WHO_NMH_NPH_02.8.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y